

Review

Exploring the role of extracellular vesicles in otorhinolaryngology: From diagnostics to therapeutic potential

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ABSTRACT

Extracellular vesicles (EVs), including exosomes and microvesicles, have gained increasing attention as cell-free platforms for diagnostics and therapy across multiple medical disciplines, including otorhinolaryngology. This narrative review surveyed PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science up to October 2025, with an emphasis on studies published within the past decade, to summarize and critically evaluate the mechanistic, diagnostic, and therapeutic roles of EVs in otorhinolaryngologic disorders. Current evidence, which is predominantly preclinical with a limited number of early-phase clinical studies, supports the potential utility of EVs in several disease contexts. In head and neck cancers, EVs show value as biomarkers for early detection, disease staging, and monitoring treatment response. In sensorineural hearing loss, EVs, particularly those derived from mesenchymal stem cells, demonstrate anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and neuroprotective properties that support cochlear repair and neural regeneration. Similarly, EV-mediated modulation of chondrocyte function and extracellular matrix synthesis provides a preclinical foundation for cartilage and reconstructive applications. Emerging studies also suggests diagnostic and therapeutic roles for EVs in chronic rhinosinusitis and olfactory dysfunction, mainly through immune modulation and mucosal repair. Intranasal administration has shown promise as a non-invasive

Abbreviations: EV(s), Extracellular vesicle(s); sEV(s), Small extracellular vesicle(s); SEC, Size exclusion chromatography; MVE(s), Multivesicular endosome(s); HNC(s), Head and neck cancer(s); OSCC, Oral squamous cell carcinoma; HPV, Human papillomavirus; RNAseq, RNA sequencing; NPC, Nasopharyngeal carcinoma; CYP A, Cyclophilin A; lncRNA(s), Long noncoding RNA(s); miRNA(s), microRNA(s); mRNA(s), messenger RNA(s); CHP, Chondrocyte-homing peptide; ACAN, Aggrecan; SOX-9, SRY-box transcription factor 9; TUNEL, Terminal deoxynucleotidyl transferase dUTP nick end labeling; GMP, Good manufacturing practice; Ce6, Chlorin e6; USMB, Ultrasound combined with microbubbles; UC-MSCs, Umbilical Cord Mesenchymal Stem Cells; BM-MSC, Bone marrow-derived MSC; HEI-OC1, House Ear Institute-Organ of Corti 1; CSGPCs, Cochlear spiral ganglion progenitor cells; ABR, Auditory brainstem response; SNHL, Sensorineural hearing loss; NIHL, Noise-induced hearing loss; ARHL, Age-related hearing loss; BDNF, Brain-derived neurotrophic factor; SGN(s), Spiral ganglion neuron(s); BLB, Blood-labyrinth barrier; ROS, Reactive oxygen species; CAF, Cancer-associated fibroblast; EBV, Epstein-Barr virus; TME, Tumor microenvironment; TAM, Tumor-associated macrophage; MDSC, Myeloid-derived suppressor cell; Treg, Regulatory T cell; TiN, Tumor-infiltrating nerve; TiM, Tumor-infiltrating microbe; PD-L1, Programmed cell death-ligand 1; PD-1, Programmed cell death protein 1; EMT, Epithelial-mesenchymal transition; AAV, Adeno-associated virus; IRI, Ischemia-Reperfusion Injury; hWJ-MSCs, Human umbilical cord Wharton's jelly mesenchymal stem cells.

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delivery route in experimental models, particularly for targeting neural and nasal tissues. Despite these encouraging findings, major challenges remain, including limited clinical validation, variability in EV isolation and characterisation methods, and the need for scalable, standardised production. Addressing these gaps through coordinated translational and clinical research will be critical for advancing EV-based applications in otorhinolaryngology.

1. Introduction

Extracellular vesicles (EVs) are a heterogeneous group of lipid bilayer-enclosed particles that carry diverse molecular cargo, including proteins, metabolites, lipids, and nucleic acids. Once considered mere cellular debris, EVs are now recognized as critical mediators of intercellular communication, largely due to their distinctive cargo composition (Kumar et al., 2024; Xie et al., 2019). EVs are released by various cell types across different tissues, and their cellular origin strongly influences both their molecular content and functional roles (Kumar et al., 2024).

EVs are mainly classified by biogenesis (exosomes, microvesicles, apoptotic EVs, and autophagic EVs), size, and specialized functions (Sheta et al., 2023). Exosomes are produced through the fusion of multivesicular endosomes (MVEs) with the plasma membrane and are categorized as small EVs (sEVs), typically ranging from 40 to 150 nm in diameter. In contrast, microvesicles bud directly from the plasma membrane and can range in size from 150 to 1000 nm. Apoptotic EVs are released during programmed cell death, and their size can range from 30 nm for apoptotic exosome-like vesicles to 5000 nm for apoptotic bodies (Fig. 1). Autophagic EVs, formed through the fusion of autophagosomes with endosomes, also display variable sizes (Sheta et al., 2023; Raposo and Stoorvogel, 2013). Due to the heterogeneity of extracellular vesicles and the methodological variability of studies involving them, the International Society for Extracellular Vesicles

introduced the Minimal Information for Studies of Extracellular Vesicles (MISEV) guidelines in 2014, which were later updated in 2018. These guidelines recommend using “extracellular vesicle” as the general term, while classifying specific subtypes according to their physical or biochemical properties and/or their origin or experimental conditions. They also emphasize that isolation or separation procedures must be described in sufficient detail to ensure reproducibility (Théry et al., 2018).

The choice of isolation method for EVs is crucial, as it significantly affects the yield and purity of the isolated vesicles (Shami-Shah et al., 2023). Ultracentrifugation is a long-established and widely used method for EV isolation, as it is a simple and inexpensive technique (Shami-Shah et al., 2023). However, a limitation of ultracentrifugation is that it can cause aggregation of small and large EVs (Linares et al., 2015) and even alter their functionality. Size exclusion chromatography (SEC) is another commonly used isolation method that separates molecules based on their size or hydrodynamic radius by passing them through porous beads of defined sizes. Molecular aggregates and EVs that are too large to enter the pores are excluded from the pore volume and travel through the column more quickly in the mobile phase that flows between the beads. Unlike ultracentrifugation, which uses high g-forces, SEC maintains the integrity and functionality of the isolated EVs (Linares et al., 2015). However, its main drawback is that it cannot differentiate between microvesicles and exosomes of the same size (Sidhom et al., 2020). Other isolation techniques include density gradient centrifugation, dual-

Fig. 1. Formation and release of exosomes, microvesicles, and apoptotic vesicles. Exosomes are formed through the endosomal pathway. The cell membrane buds inward to create early endosomes, which mature into multivesicular bodies containing intraluminal vesicles. Multivesicular bodies can either fuse with lysosomes for degradation or with the plasma membrane to release exosomes. Two main mechanisms drive this process: the ESCRT-dependent pathway (involving ESCRT-0, I, II, III, and Vps4 complexes) and an ESCRT-independent pathway, which relies on sphingolipid metabolism to generate ceramides that promote vesicle budding. Reused with permission from (Du et al., 2023). Copyright © 2023, Springer Nature.

mode chromatography, magnetic bead-based, and microfluidics-based methods (Shami-Shah et al., 2023).

In recent years, EVs, particularly exosomes, have attracted significant interest for their diverse range of clinical applications. Over 60,000 articles have mentioned EVs, with more than half of them published in the last five years. Since EVs are stable, cell-derived particles that circulate in body fluids and reflect the state of their origin cell, they have been studied as biomarkers for the early diagnosis and prognosis of various conditions, such as cancer, cardiovascular diseases, central nervous system disorders, and tuberculosis. Notably, an exosome-based diagnostic test is already available clinically for non-small cell lung cancer (Zhang et al., 2020). In addition, EVs hold considerable promise as nanocarriers for drug delivery, offering enhanced biocompatibility, stability, and reduced toxicity compared to conventional delivery systems like synthetic polymer nanoparticles or liposomes (Wang et al., 2013; Dad et al., 2021). Moreover, traditional stem cell therapies face significant challenges, including graft rejection (Eliopoulos et al., 2005) and the risk of tumorigenesis (Jeong et al., 2011). EVs have emerged as a result of the challenges in cell therapy. They have emerged as safer, cell-free alternatives. Research has shown that stem cell-derived EVs retain the therapeutic benefits of their parent cells while mitigating the associated risks of tumorigenicity and immunogenicity (Jafarinia et al., 2020; Liang et al., 2014).

Since EVs can overcome the challenges associated with cell therapies, they have emerged as attractive therapeutic candidates for research across medical specialties. In otorhinolaryngology, the unique characteristics of EVs suggest potential diagnostic and therapeutic applications, although current evidence is largely preclinical. One major challenge in this field is effective drug delivery to the inner ear. The blood-labyrinth barrier (BLB) restricts systemic drug access, while the complex anatomy of the inner ear makes the local administration challenging. To address this, several studies have investigated the potential of EVs as carriers for inner ear drug delivery (Zhang et al., 2024). Moreover, the regenerative potential of mesenchymal stem cell (MSC)-derived EVs in the inner ear has drawn growing interest. For instance, one study showed that MSC-derived EVs have protective effects on outer hair cells in cisplatin-injected mice (Tsai et al., 2021). Another *in vivo* study demonstrated that MSC-derived EVs can protect hair cells from noise-induced damage (Warnecke et al., 2020). A study demonstrated that scaffolds integrated with exosomes can effectively enhance tympanic membrane regeneration (Chahsetareh et al., 2024).

Another extensively studied application of EVs in otorhinolaryngology is their use for the diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment of head and neck cancers. For example, salivary EVs have been studied as non-invasive biomarkers for the early detection of these cancers (Owecki et al., 2025). Additionally, specific EV-derived proteins have been explored as prognostic indicators (Xie et al., 2019). Furthermore, the potential of EVs as drug delivery vehicles for targeted therapy in head and neck cancers has also been actively studied. Beyond these applications, EVs are also being studied in other areas of otorhinolaryngology for their therapeutic potential. Their anti-inflammatory and regenerative properties are being explored for the treatment of chronic rhinosinusitis and for enhancing vocal fold repair. Overall, EVs are being investigated for use in diagnostics, drug delivery, and regenerative therapies across various medical fields, with ongoing efforts to establish clinical efficacy.

This narrative review focuses specifically on the potential benefits of EVs within the field of otorhinolaryngology. Despite encouraging progress, further research is required to overcome the challenges associated with clinical translation. We conducted a literature search in PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science up to October 2025, prioritizing studies from the past 5–10 years that explored the mechanistic roles, diagnostic applications, and therapeutic uses of EVs in otorhinolaryngologic disorders. This review summarizes recent advances and highlights future directions for EV-based applications in the field, including head and neck cancers, hearing loss and inner ear disorders,

chronic rhinosinusitis, and vocal fold repair.

2. Mechanisms of extracellular vesicle function in otorhinolaryngology

Different mechanisms have been proposed to explain the role of EVs in cell regeneration and tissue repair (Table S1). Inflammation is a critical component of the repair process following tissue injury. However, maintaining a delicate balance is essential, as persistent or uncontrolled inflammation can exacerbate damage and impair healing (Wilkinson and Hardman, 2020). EVs can modulate inflammation in damaged tissue of animal models through multiple pathways. These include influencing macrophage polarization, suppressing the release of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-1 β , IL-6, TNF- α , and IL-12p40, inducing the release of anti-inflammatory cytokines like IL-10 and TGF- β 1, and regulating the TLR4/NF- κ B/STAT3/AKT signaling pathway (Fig. 2) (Ti et al., 2015; Zhang et al., 2014). EVs can also reduce oxidative stress in animal and cell models by limiting the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) by regulation of the NRF2 signaling pathway (Wang et al., 2020). Another key aspect of tissue repair is angiogenesis, which supplies the metabolic demands of healing tissue (Wilkinson and Hardman, 2020). Several preclinical studies have demonstrated that EVs can stimulate angiogenesis (Merino-Gonzalez et al., 2016). They contain pro-angiogenic factors such as VEGF, TGF- β 1, and IL-8 (Merino-Gonzalez et al., 2016), and can also transport WNT4, which activates the WNT/ β -catenin pathway to promote new vessel formation (Zhang et al., 2015). In addition, EVs have been implicated in angiogenesis through modulation of the PI3K/AKT/ENOS pathway (Hu et al., 2021). Hepatocyte growth factor (HGF) is another critical regulator of tissue repair, recognized for its role in restoring normal tissue architecture during organ regeneration (Matsumoto and Nakamura, 1993). EVs can deliver RNA that induce the production of HGF in rat tubular cells, thereby promoting cell dedifferentiation and growth (Ju et al., 2015). Together, these mechanisms highlight the therapeutic potential of EVs in treating otorhinolaryngological disorders such as chronic otitis media, hearing loss, and nasal mucosal injuries, where controlling inflammation, stimulating angiogenesis, and facilitating tissue regeneration are essential.

3. EVs in head and neck cancer treatment

Head and neck cancer (HNC) is the sixth most diagnosed cancer, with 946,456 new cases and 482,001 deaths reported in 2022 worldwide (Bray et al., 2024). HNC comprises a diverse group of malignancies arising from the oral cavity, pharynx (including the nasopharynx, oropharynx, and hypopharynx), larynx, nasal cavity, paranasal sinuses, and major salivary glands (Chow, 2020). The overall 5-year survival rate for all HNCs ranges from 50% to 60%, with site of malignancy, age, and tumor stage serving as the primary prognostic factors (Heinolainen et al., 2025; Cadoni et al., 2017).

In recent years, studies have demonstrated that exosomes can contribute to cancer progression by interacting with various components of the tumor microenvironment (TME) through their diverse array of cargo, downregulating the immune response (Rodriguez Zorrilla et al., 2019). They can also carry factors contributing to angiogenesis and epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT), as a prelude to metastasis (Mastronikolis et al., 2023). This section will further discuss the role of exosomes in the pathogenesis of HNCs, their involvement in treatment resistance, and their potential use as biomarkers for diagnostic and prognostic purposes (Fig. 3).

3.1. Role of exosomes in HNC pathogenesis

3.1.1. Tumor progression and proliferation

Tumor progression is a complex process involving various cell types and multiple mechanisms. Exosomes can contribute to tumor

Fig. 2. Mechanisms of extracellular vesicle function in wound healing. EVs can contribute to wound healing through inducing angiogenesis, tissue regeneration, and secreting anti-inflammatory factors. Reused with permission from (Zhou et al., 2023). Copyright © 2023, Springer Nature.

progression through various mechanisms. For instance, Hou et al. reported that exosomal SNHG16 from nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC) cells promotes tumor progression via the micro ribonucleic acid (miR)-23b-5p/MCM6 pathway (Hou et al., 2024). Another study on NPC revealed that exosomes rich in miR-103a-3p directly target the metabolic enzyme acyl-CoA oxidase 1 (ACOX-1). This enzyme upregulates lipid droplet accumulation, thereby stimulating tumor progression (Shan et al., 2024). Moreover, a study on oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) observed that exosomal miR-24-3p promotes the proliferation of tumor cells (He et al., 2020).

3.1.2. Angiogenesis

Angiogenesis is a critical process in tumor progression, as it provides cancer cells with nutrients necessary for their growth. The role of tumor-derived exosomes in promoting angiogenesis in HNC has been widely discussed (Ludwig et al., 2018; Tengler et al., 2023). Correspondingly, multiple exosomal cargoes have been discussed for their role in neo-angiogenesis in HNCs. Capik et al. reported that miR-1825 levels increase in HNC cells in response to hypoxia. These cells secrete exosomes containing miR-1825, which promote the angiogenic potential of endothelial cells through the miR-1825/TSC2/mTOR axis (Capik et al., 2023). Ludwig et al. investigated the role of TGF β , abundant in extracellular vesicles (EVs) secreted from HNC cells. They concluded that TGF β promotes macrophages to a proangiogenic type and increases the release of pro-angiogenic factors from them (Ludwig et al., 2022).

In nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC), exosomal miR-23a has been shown to suppress TSGA10, a gene that functions as an anti-angiogenic/tumor-suppressive factor, and thereby enhances endothelial tube formation *in vitro* and neovascularization *in vivo* (Bao et al., 2018). Also, exosomal miR-17-5p released from NPC has been shown to down-regulate BAMBI (BMP and membrane-bound inhibitor), thereby inducing a pro-angiogenic signaling in endothelial and tumor cells and promoting endothelial migration and tubulogenesis (Duan et al., 2019).

Furthermore, HNSCC-derived EVs are loaded with the receptor EPHB2 that interacts with ephrin-B expressed on endothelial cells,

thereby triggering angiogenesis via STAT3 phosphorylation/activation (Sato et al., 2019). NPC-derived EVs are also enriched with PFKFB3, a key glycolytic regulator that boosts endothelial glycolytic flux and therewith allows angiogenesis (Gu et al., 2017). These findings show that the EV cargo, like miRNAs (miR-23a, miR-17-5p), membrane receptors (EPHB2), and metabolic enzymes (PFKFB3), probably act complementary manner on endothelial signal transduction, metabolism, and gene expression to drive angiogenesis across head and neck cancer subtypes (Fig. 3) (Huang et al., 2021).

3.1.3. Epithelial–mesenchymal transition and metastasis

EMT is a dynamic biological process in which epithelial cells acquire mesenchymal characteristics, enabling enhanced motility, invasiveness, and resistance to apoptosis. By disrupting cell–cell adhesion and promoting cytoskeletal reorganization, EMT facilitates tumor cell dissemination from the primary site, serving as a key mechanism in cancer metastasis (Nieto et al., 2016; Lamouille et al., 2014). Research by Ye et al. indicates that exosomes released by cancer-associated fibroblasts (CAFs) in OSCCs contain elevated levels of PIWI-interacting RNAs (piR)-35462, which upregulates fat mass and obesity-associated protein (FTO) in cancer cells. This increase in FTO suppresses N6-methyladenosine (m6A) RNA methylation, thereby enhancing the stability and expression of Twist1 mRNA, ultimately promoting EMT and driving tumor progression (Ye et al., 2025). Additionally, Li et al. reported that hypoxic OSCC cells produce exosomes rich in miR-21, which also promote EMT and are closely associated with lymph node metastasis (Li et al., 2016). Furthermore, another study reported that exosomal miR-155 contributes to the EMT process in OSCC by significantly reducing E-cadherin expression while simultaneously increasing the expression of N-cadherin, vimentin, and Twist (Kirave et al., 2020). The role of exosomes in EMT has also been studied in NPC, where exosomal miR-103a-3p has been shown to improve EMT progression and the migration of tumor cells (Shan et al., 2024).

Fig. 3. Exosomes derived from cancer cells, cancer-associated fibroblasts (CAFs), and tumor-associated macrophages (TAMs) are key mediators of tumor progression in HNC. These nanosized extracellular vesicles facilitate intercellular communication within the tumor microenvironment (TME). Exosomes promote cancer cell proliferation and survival, inhibit apoptosis, and drive epithelial–mesenchymal transition (EMT). They also contribute to angiogenesis, immune evasion, and extensive TME remodeling by reprogramming stromal and immune cells, including CAFs, TAMs, myeloid-derived suppressor cells (MDSCs), and regulatory T cells (Tregs). Collectively, these processes enhance tumor aggressiveness, metastasis, and therapeutic resistance in HNC.

3.1.4. Immune evasion

Beyond mechanisms related to cytokine signaling and activation of TME components separately discussed, tumor-derived exosomes further contribute to immune evasion by carrying immune checkpoint molecules such as programmed cell death ligand 1 (PD-L1) on their surface, thereby suppressing antitumor immune responses. Notably, Theodoraki et al. demonstrated that exosomal PD-L1 suppresses CD69 expression on T cells in HNC (Theodoraki et al., 2018). These findings suggest that the effects of PD-L1/PD-1 extend beyond direct cell–cell interactions, as tumor-derived exosomes displaying PD-L1 on their surface can also exert similar immunosuppressive effects. They also discovered that levels of exosomal PD-L1 correlate with the cancer stage (Theodoraki et al., 2018).

3.1.5. Interaction with tumor microenvironment components

Generally speaking, cancer cells dynamically interact with their microenvironment, modifying it to support their progression and growth (Fig. 3). This microenvironment is referred to as the TME and is composed of a diverse array of cell types, including CAFs, tumor-associated macrophages (TAMs), myeloid-derived suppressor cells (MDSCs), tumor-associated neutrophils (TANs), regulatory T cells (Tregs), and tumor-infiltrating nerves (TiNs) (Taghizadeh-Hesary,

2024). In addition, in the context of head and neck tumors, tumor-infiltrating microbes (TiMs) can increase this complexity through interactions with cancer cells and other TME components (Ashique et al., 2024). This section is dedicated to revealing these complex interactions.

3.1.5.1. Cancer-associated fibroblasts. Exosomes play a crucial role in cancer progression by interacting with components of the cancer microenvironment. CAFs are one of these components, promoting tumor invasion, proliferation, and metastasis through proinflammatory factors. CAFs are transitioned from in-situ normal fibroblasts (NF) or bone marrow-derived mesenchymal stem cells (Yang et al., 2019). Several exosomal non-coding RNAs and proteins have been implicated in mediating this transition in various cancers (Yang et al., 2019; Mito et al., 2023). A recent functional study using xenograft models and knockdown assays found that hypoxic HNC cells produce hypoxia-inducible factor 1 subunit alpha (HIF-1α). This factor upregulates the transcription of miR-21, leading to the release of exosomes containing miR-21 from the cancer cells. These exosomes subsequently targeted YOD1 genes, initiating the transition of NFs to CAFs (Ye et al., 2023). Another study on HNCs demonstrated that HIF-1α triggers the release of miR5100-rich exosomes from cancer cells, which in turn activate the

QKI/AKT/STAT3 pathway, leading to the activation of CAFs (Duan et al., 2024). A study on OSCCs revealed that CAFs activated by OSCC-derived EVs exhibit distinct characteristics compared to those activated by TGF- β signaling. EV-induced CAFs had high expression of inflammatory genes and secreted significantly more pro-inflammatory cytokines, especially IL-8 and CXCL5, compared to TGF- β -induced CAFs (Arebro et al., 2023). In contrast, Wang et al. reported that HPV-positive HNC cells release exosomes enriched with miR-9-5p, which suppresses TGF- β -mediated fibroblast transformation. This miRNA inhibits TGF- β signaling-driven phenotypic transformation of fibroblasts, which could account for the better prognosis seen in HPV-positive cancers (Wang et al., 2022).

The role of exosomes extends beyond the activation of CAFs, as they can also be secreted by CAFs themselves, facilitating their intercellular communications. For instance, Qi et al. demonstrated that CAF-derived exosomes deliver miR-196a to tumor cells. This miRNA inhibits the expression of the CDKN1B and ING5 genes in HNC cells, which in turn promotes cisplatin resistance in these cells (Qin et al., 2019). While these examples highlight tumor-promoting effects driven by the enrichment of specific miRNAs in exosomes, other findings indicate that a decrease in certain exosomal miRNAs in CAFs also contributes to their pathology. Specifically, miR-3188 expression is markedly reduced in exosomes and their parental CAFs from HNC tissues. miR-3188 can be transferred from fibroblasts to HNC cells via exosomes, influencing proliferation and apoptosis by directly targeting B-cell lymphoma 2 (BCL2) both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Notably, miR-3188-loaded exosomes significantly inhibit tumor growth *in vivo*, suggesting that the loss of miR-3188 in CAF-derived exosomes facilitates the malignant phenotypes of HNC cells through the depression of BCL2 (Wang et al., 2019). Similarly, Li et al. reported that decreased levels of miR-34a-5p in CAF-derived exosomes are associated with enhanced cancer aggressiveness (Li et al., 2018).

3.1.5.2. Microbiome. The microbiome can influence HNC cell metabolism and tumor progression indirectly by modulating host immune responses and cytokine release, or directly through microbial infiltration into the tumor and interaction with cancer cells and other components of the TME (Ashique et al., 2024). Recent studies show that exosomes derived from Epstein-Barr virus (EBV)-positive NPC cells contain latent membrane protein 1 (LMP1) and fibroblast activation protein alpha (FAP α). These exosomes activate YAP1 signaling in fibroblasts, which promotes fibrosis and tumor progression. Consequently, the activated fibroblasts secrete immunosuppressive cytokines, including IL-8, CCL2, and IL-6, contributing to tumor growth and immune evasion by enhancing resistance to T cell-mediated cytotoxicity (Lee et al., 2022).

3.1.5.3. Myeloid-derived suppressor cells. TME also consists of several immunologic components, such as MDSCs, TAMs, and Tregs, which play pivotal roles in blocking anti-tumor immune response and promoting tumor progression. MDSCs are a heterogeneous population of immature myeloid cells that have undergone pathological changes and possess strong immunosuppressive capabilities (Veglia et al., 2021). It has been demonstrated that hypoxic OSCC cells can secrete exosomes, which intensify the immunosuppressive effect of MDSCs through the miR-21/PTEN/PD-L1 pathway (Li et al., 2019). A study by He et al. in HNCs found that cancer cell-derived exosomes containing UBL3 and ANGPTL1 can contribute to an increased population of MDSCs (He et al., 2025).

3.1.5.4. Tumor-associated macrophages. TAMs are a major type of immune cells found within the TME and are broadly divided into two functional subtypes: M1 and M2 macrophages. M1 macrophages typically have anti-tumor effects. In contrast, M2 macrophages support tumor growth by promoting metastasis, suppressing T cell responses, angiogenesis, and advancing tumor progression. Importantly, M1 and M2 macrophages are highly adaptable and can switch between forms in response to changes in the TME or treatments (Pan et al., 2020).

Exosomes have been found to serve an essential function in their polarization. Animal studies have shown that following endoplasmic reticulum (ER) stress, OSCC cells secrete programmed cell death ligand 1 (PD-L1) exosomes, which upregulate PD-L1 expression in macrophages, promoting their polarization toward the M2 phenotype (Yuan et al., 2022). Another study on laryngeal cancer cells revealed that exosomes can induce interleukin (IL)-10 in macrophages and expression of PD-L1 on tumor cells, promoting an immunosuppressive environment (Bellmunt et al., 2019). Further study on laryngeal cancer also revealed that exosomes from laryngeal cancer cells contain miR-1246, which promotes M2 polarization (Wu et al., 2022). Theodoraki et al. studied human exosomes isolated from HNC patients and discovered that when these exosomes are taken up by macrophages, they trigger a strong type 2 like polarization. This process is accompanied by an increase in the secretion of CXCL4 (Theodoraki et al., 2024). Moreover, a study by Chen et al. also demonstrated that exosomal AC068768.1 derived from laryngeal carcinoma cells promotes M2 polarization and tumor invasiveness (Chen et al., 2024). This effect of exosomes on macrophage polarization has also been studied in NPC, where exosomes rich in TP73-AS1 induce M2 polarization and promote the motility and tube formation of macrophages (Yao et al., 2022). An experimental study demonstrated that exosome-induced M1-like phenotype can also be protumoral. This study on OSCC cells revealed that cancer cells can also secrete exosomes carrying thrombospondin-1 (THBS1), which, upon uptake by macrophages, activate p38, Akt, and SAPK/JNK signaling pathways, promoting macrophage polarization toward an M1-like phenotype (Xiao et al., 2018). Notably, Yadav et al. discovered that HPV-negative cells secrete exosomes that can regulate the STAT1, NF- κ B, and AP-1 pathways and promote M1 polarization, in contrast to HPV-positive exosomes, which induce a mixed M1 and M2 polarization (Yadav et al., 2025).

Additionally, exosomes secreted from TAMs also have potential effects on cancer cells and the TME. For instance, a study found that TAM-derived exosomes can promote EMT in HNCs by upregulating miR4435-2HG (Liu et al., 2025). Another study discovered that TAM-derived exosomes carry miR-21-5p, a miRNA that has been shown to promote angiogenesis in HNCs through the YAP1/HIF-1 α pathway (Yan et al., 2024). TAM-derived exosomes can also exhibit tumor-suppressive properties. Jiang et al. reported that M1 macrophage-derived exosomes contain the long noncoding RNA HOXA transcript at the distal tip (HOTTIP), which activates the TLR5/NF- κ B pathway and inhibits HNC progression (Jiang et al., 2022).

3.1.5.5. Regulatory T cells. In addition to TAMs and MDSCs, Tregs also contribute to immunosuppression within the TME. Tregs are a specialized subset of CD4⁺ T cells that maintain immune homeostasis by suppressing excessive or autoreactive immune responses. They can promote tumor progression by suppressing the immune response against tumor cells (Togashi and Nishikawa, 2017). Wei et al. demonstrated that PD-L1 carried on exosomes secreted by HNC cells not only promotes M2 macrophage polarization but also promotes CD4⁺ T cell polarization to Tregs. These PD-L1 exosomes amplify the positive feedback loop of aTreg-M2, inhibiting the proliferation of CD4⁺CD25⁻ T cells and facilitating immune evasion of the tumor (Wei et al., 2023). Furthermore, Schuler et al. found that within the TME, CD4⁺CD39⁺ Tregs convert exogenous adenosine triphosphate (ATP) into immunosuppressive adenosine upon interaction with CD39⁺CD73⁺ exosomes (Schuler et al., 2014). Muller et al. also documented this process, concluding that exosomes influence Tregs through surface signaling and do not require internalization to exert their effects (Muller et al., 2017).

3.1.5.6. Tumor-infiltrating nerves. Another important component of the TME is TiNs, which directly contribute to tumor proliferation and correlate with poor patient survival (Gysler and Drapkin, 2021). TiNs can enhance the metabolic plasticity and metastatic ability of cancer

cells by transferring mitochondria to them (Hoover et al., 2025). Experiments on HNC have demonstrated that cancer-derived exosomes can stimulate tumor innervation. Restaino et al. investigated CCND1 and PIK3CA genes in HNC survival and observed that CCND1 expression in cancer cells increases the secretion of miR-21-5p and miR-15b-5p in exosomes. These exosomes enhance tumor innervation and metastasis to draining lymph nodes via the PTEN/AKT pathway (Restaino et al., 2024).

In summary, exosomes are key facilitators of HNC pathogenesis by promoting the transformation of NFs into tumor-supportive fibroblasts, modulating immune cell behavior to favor immune evasion, enhancing tumor angiogenesis, and driving EMT (Table S2). Through these multifaceted mechanisms, exosomes significantly contribute to tumor initiation, progression, and metastasis, making them crucial players in the molecular pathways underlying head and neck cancer development.

3.2. Role of exosomes in HNC treatment resistance

3.2.1. Radiotherapy

Radiotherapy is the mainstay of HNC treatment. About 80% of patients with HNC receive radiotherapy during their treatment course (Borras et al., 2015). One challenging issue in the treatment of patients with HNC is that they show a wide range of treatment responses to radiation. This may be in part due to the intrinsic radiosensitivity of cancer cells. (Steel et al., 1989). Emerging evidence has revealed the role of exosome cargoes in improving the radioresistance of HNC cells. In a study by Mutschelknaus et al., radiation exposure of two HNC cell lines (BHY and FaDu) significantly increased both exosome secretion and uptake by tumor cells. These exosomes, in turn, have a notable impact on the repair of DNA double-strand breaks (DSB) in irradiated cells (Mutschelknaus et al., 2016). Another study discovered that radiation significantly alters the protein cargo of exosomes, which subsequently enhances AKT signaling. This increase in signaling boosts the motility of BHY and FaDu cells, suggesting that exosomes may play a role in the progression of HNC during radiotherapy (Mutschelknaus et al., 2017). BAK, a protein from the BCL-2 family, plays a critical role in mitochondrial apoptosis in response to radiation (Cao et al., 2019). A recent study found that exosomes released from radioresistant OSCC cells contain miR-503-3p. This microRNA inhibits BAK, thereby impairing the caspase cascade and suppressing the effects of radiation on radiosensitive cells (Yamana et al., 2021). As noted above, various exosomal cargoes can promote the EMT in HNC cells, a process that plays a central role in enhancing their radioresistance (Houshyari, 2024). Therefore, exosomes can contribute to HNC cells' radioresistance through a myriad of mechanisms.

3.2.2. Chemotherapy

Cytotoxic chemotherapeutics constitute the mainstay of HNC treatment, either in combination with radiotherapy, as a standalone treatment for the induction chemotherapy, or as systemic treatment in metastatic disease (Ameri et al., 2022). Cisplatin is the first-line and most commonly used chemotherapeutic for OSCC; however, drug resistance to cisplatin significantly hinders its therapeutic potential (Cheng et al., 2021). Studies have shown that suppressing the secretion of exosomes alleviates cisplatin resistance in HNC cells (Khoo et al., 2019; Ogawa et al., 2024). For example, Liu et al. discovered that exosomes derived from cisplatin-resistant OSCC cells contain miR-21. They found that these exosomes can diminish DNA damage signaling and promote chemoresistance to cisplatin in other OSCC cells (Liu et al., 2017). Additionally, another study noted the upregulation of miR-155 in exosomes released from cisplatin-resistant cells, although its specific role in chemoresistance remains unclear (Kirave et al., 2020). Furthermore, Qin et al. showed that CAFs are innately resistant to cisplatin. They found that CAFs release exosomes containing miR-196a, which binds to CDKN1B and ING5 in HNC cells, thus promoting cisplatin resistance in cancer cells (Qin et al., 2019). Moreover, a recent study

identified two subtypes of CAFs in HNCs. CAF-P is linked to promoting tumor progression, while CAF-D is associated with moderately delaying it. This study noted that CAF-P releases exosomes rich in miR-876-3p, which downregulates GATA1 expression. GATA1 is a likely transcription factor for IGF1R3, which correlates positively with sensitivity to cisplatin (Kang et al., 2024). Besides miRs, other exosomal cargoes have been linked to cisplatin resistance. For example, Hoo et al. noted different exosomal proteomes in cisplatin-resistant cell lines. Moreover, they found that exosomes released from these resistant lines contained significantly higher levels of cisplatin, demonstrating their role in drug resistance through active drug transportation (Khoo et al., 2019).

3.2.3. Targeted therapies

Targeted therapies, which selectively inhibit key molecular pathways involved in tumor progression, have emerged as important adjuncts to conventional modalities in HNC, and are increasingly integrated into contemporary treatment strategies (Li et al., 2023). Erlotinib is an oral inhibitor of the epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR). EGFR is markedly elevated in HNCs and significantly correlates with chemoresistance and poor survival rates (Rubin Grandis et al., 1998). While early studies suggested that EGFR inhibition therapies could be effective in HNCs (Gross et al., 2014), subsequent clinical trials demonstrated only modest response rates (Soulieres et al., 2004), indicating resistance to erlotinib in HNC cells. A study by Zheng et al. found that exosomes from erlotinib-resistant cells exhibit increased levels of pro-tumorigenic miRNAs, specifically miR-7704, miR-21-5p, and miR-3960. They also discovered that EVs secreted from these cells contain upregulated miRs with possible immunosuppressive effects (Zheng et al., 2020).

3.2.4. Immunotherapy

While the role of exosomes in immunosuppression has been extensively studied and discussed earlier in this article, their involvement in the resistance to immunotherapy in HNCs remains unexplored. A recent study (NCT04453046) aimed to deplete plasma exosomes in patients with head and neck cancer using an exosome-specific hemopurifier and to evaluate its impact on pembrolizumab efficacy. However, the trial was terminated due to a lack of eligible participants at the study site (Depleting Exosomes to Improve Response to Immune Therapy in Head and Neck Squamous Cell Cancer).

Given the established role of EVs in mediating resistance to radiotherapy and chemotherapy, targeting EV-mediated pathways has emerged as a novel therapeutic frontier. Potential intervention strategies can be broadly categorized into four approaches: (Kumar et al., 2024) inhibition of EV biogenesis or secretion, (Xie et al., 2019) depletion of circulating EVs, (Sheta et al., 2023) neutralization of pathogenic EV cargo, and (Raposo and Stoorvogel, 2013) exploitation of EVs as delivery vehicles for anti-resistance agents. Although several of these strategies have been investigated in other disease settings (Catalano and O'Driscoll, 2020; Usman et al., 2018), their translation to HNCs remains limited. To date, the only EV-targeting strategy evaluated in HNCs is a hemopurifier-based approach designed to deplete circulating EVs; however, this trial was discontinued due to poor patient enrollment (Depleting Exosomes to Improve Response to Immune Therapy in Head and Neck Squamous Cell Cancer).

3.3. Exosomes as biomarkers in HNC

3.3.1. Diagnosis

Early diagnosis of HNC is crucial for initiating treatment and improving prognosis. Many studies have investigated the role of exosomes in saliva as a non-invasive and easy method for diagnosing HNCs. Owecki et al. conducted a recent systematic review of 23 articles exploring the role of salivary exosomes in the diagnosis of HNCs. They concluded that various exosomal cargoes, such as multiple proteins and miRNAs, show potential for the early diagnosis of HNCs (Owecki et al.,

2025). Nevertheless, further research involving larger populations is necessary to assess the clinical applicability of this method as an early diagnostic tool for HNCs.

Other studies have also explored the use of exosomes in circulation as diagnostic methods. For instance, Jiang et al. reported several exosomal miRNAs in plasma as potential biomarkers for the diagnosis of NPC (Jiang et al., 2021). Another study found that exosomal BART13-3p in circulation serves as a superior diagnostic method for NPC compared to traditional serologic methods (Ramayanti et al., 2019). Additionally, Cyclophilin A (CYPA) found in circulating exosomes has also been investigated as an effective diagnostic tool for NPC detection (Liu et al., 2019).

3.3.2. Prognosis

Several studies have also explored the role of exosomes as potential biomarkers for cancer prognosis. Theodoraki et al. reported that CD44v3+ exosomes contain higher levels of immunosuppressive cargo and EGFR in HNCs. They concluded that these exosomes are associated with poor cancer prognosis and could serve as biomarkers for disease staging (Theodoraki et al., 2020). Another study on HNCs discovered that patients with stage 3 or 4 tumors had higher levels of the Fc receptor CD16 in their plasma exosomes compared to those with stage 1 or 2 tumors. This suggests that CD16-rich exosomes may serve as prognostic biomarkers for tumor stage (Hofmann et al., 2020). Additionally, Patel et al. identified a correlation between exosomes with elevated levels of miR-1307-5p and a poor prognosis in oral cancer (Patel et al., 2022). In another recent study, Patel's team also identified a combination of three miRNAs (miR-140-5p, miR-143-5p, and miR-145-5p) in the salivary exosomes of patients with OSCC. This combination showed promise as a prognostic factor and exhibited high efficacy in predicting tumor progression (Patel et al., 2023). Moreover, Ono et al. reported that exosomes containing heat shock proteins correlate with metastatic OSCC, highlighting their potential as biomarkers for cancer progression (Ono et al., 2018). Notably, the use of long noncoding RNAs (lncRNAs) found in exosomes as potential biomarkers has also been explored. Liu et al. identified 17 lncRNAs with significant prognostic value in HNCs (Liu et al., 2024). Nevertheless, the clinical applicability of these exosomal prognostic biomarkers needs further large-scale studies to be validated.

3.3.3. Treatment response and follow-up

Another explored role for exosomes as biomarkers in HNCs is in evaluating the treatment response of patients. Rodríguez-Zorrilla et al. analyzed plasma exosomes before, during, and after surgical treatment of OSCC patients. They observed a significant reduction in plasma exosomes post-surgery, with higher concentrations after surgery correlating with tumor relapse (Rodríguez-Zorrilla et al., 2023). This relationship between post-treatment exosome levels and treatment response has also been noted in patients undergoing ipilimumab therapy (Theodoraki et al., 2019). Moreover, Theodoraki et al. reported that exosomal PD-L1 demonstrated early changes after treatment, effectively distinguishing between successful treatment outcomes and recurrent disease (Theodoraki et al., 2021). Similarly, Zandberg et al. investigated the role of exosomes in predicting immunotherapy outcomes and identified T cell-derived CD3(+) and tumor-enriched CD3(-) plasma small extracellular vesicles (sEVs) as potential biomarkers for assessing response to anti-PD-1 monoclonal antibody (mAb) therapy (Zandberg et al., 2024).

Although EVs hold considerable promise, translating these biomarkers into routine clinical practice faces significant practical barriers. Chief among these are preanalytical variables, including inconsistencies in sample collection, storage conditions, and processing times (Batool et al., 2023). These factors are further compounded by limited assay reproducibility across different EV isolation platforms, resulting in substantial variability in EV yield, purity, and contaminant profiles (Lawrence and Shah, 2024). Moreover, the lack of universally accepted normalization strategies presents an additional hurdle. Given the

marked heterogeneity of EV populations, identifying a reliable and validated housekeeping gene or internal control remains a major unresolved issue (Lawrence and Shah, 2024). To address these limitations and establish clinical utility, future research must move beyond small pilot investigations and prioritize large-scale, multicenter validation cohorts capable of confirming the robustness and reproducibility of EV signatures across diverse patient populations (Yekula et al., 2020).

4. Extracellular vesicles in hearing loss and inner ear disorders

Hearing loss is generally classified into conductive, sensorineural, and mixed types, with sensorineural hearing loss (SNHL) being the most common (Aasen et al., 2008). SNHL typically results from functional damage to the cochlea, auditory nerve, or auditory center, arising from the following reasons (Maimaitikelimu et al., 2025). The condition is primarily driven by irreversible injury to spiral ganglion neurons, which transmit auditory information to the brain and to the sensory hair cells of the cochlea. Damage to these structures disrupts sound transduction and neural signaling, in contrast to conductive hearing loss, which arises from mechanical dysfunction of the outer or middle ear (Capra et al., 2023; Forster et al., 2025; He et al., 2024). The etiology of SNHL is multifactorial, including noise exposure, aging, ototoxic medications, genetic mutations, infections, and systemic diseases. Among these, age-related hearing loss and noise-induced hearing loss (NIHL) are the most prevalent (Warnecke et al., 2022). Damage to the spiral ganglion neurons and cochlear hair cells is the primary cause of SNHL (Yang et al., 2021). Unlike mammalian cochlear sensory cells, some non-mammalian species exhibit robust regenerative responses after injury. Researchers are exploring external interventions to overcome the limited regenerative capacity of mammalian inner ear cells (Perde-Schrepler et al., 2024; Quan et al., 2023).

These insults trigger inflammation, apoptosis, and oxidative stress in the cochlea, ultimately leading to the loss of hair cells and neurons. Excessive reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated by ototoxic drugs can cause lipid peroxidation, DNA damage, and activation of apoptotic pathways (Perde-Schrepler et al., 2025; Chen et al., 2022; Vlajkovic et al., 2024). Cochlear injury also activates local immune responses, including macrophages and microglia (Warnecke et al., 2022). Importantly, the loss of spiral ganglion neurons and synaptic connections (synaptopathy) further disrupts auditory signal transmission, exacerbating hearing deficits beyond those caused by hair cell loss alone (Warnecke et al., 2021). At the molecular level, cochlear damage activates key inflammatory signaling pathways, such as NF- κ B, Jak-STAT, and TNF, which drive the upregulation of pro-inflammatory cytokines, including TNF- α , IL-1 β and CCL2. Chronic inflammation exacerbates cochlear damage by amplifying oxidative stress and apoptosis, ultimately leading to irreversible cell death (He et al., 2024; Chen et al., 2022). Key mediators of programmed cell death in hair cells and neurons include caspases, c-Jun N-terminal kinase (JNK), and cyclin-dependent kinases (e.g., CDK2). Experimental studies have shown that inhibiting these pathways can slow hair cell loss, underscoring their critical role in driving permanent damage (Vlajkovic et al., 2024). In addition, genetic alterations affecting cochlear ion channels, gap junctions (such as connexins), and mitochondrial function compromise hair cell survival and cochlear homeostasis, thereby increasing the risk of progressive SNHL (He et al., 2024; Adam et al., 1993). Dysfunction in autophagy and mitochondrial quality control further heightens cellular stress, leading to the accumulation of damaged proteins and organelles, which accelerates hair cell death (Chen et al., 2022). Recent studies and clinical trials have explored therapeutic strategies aimed at protecting or restoring hearing in SNHL. These include pharmacologic approaches such as methylprednisolone acetate nanogel (Amizadeh et al., 2025), edaravone (Nitta et al., 2025), SPI-1005 (Kil et al., 2014), FX-322 (McLean et al., 2021), valganciclovir (Chung et al., 2024), as well as physical rehabilitation (Zhang et al., 2025). Advances in cochlear and auditory implants, alongside emerging stem cell and drug-based

therapies, are paving the way toward more personalized treatment. Despite these advances, major challenges remain. Most current interventions focus on managing symptoms rather than regenerating cochlear structures, highlighting the need for further research into regenerative approaches for SNHL. Preclinical studies in rodent models have demonstrated encouraging regenerative and protective effects of EVs SNHL; however, significant translational barriers remain. The rodent cochlea is substantially smaller than the human cochlea (approximately 2–3 mm versus 9–10 mm in length) and differs in key anatomical and physiological features, including basilar membrane stiffness, hair cell morphology, and the distribution of spiral ganglion neuron (SGN) subtypes. These differences can influence EV uptake, biodistribution, and dosing requirements. For example, mouse SGNs contain a higher proportion of type I neurons and exhibit more robust myelination than human SGNs, potentially exaggerating the apparent neuroprotective effects of EVs in rodent models. In addition, the extremely limited volume of human perilymph, typically only 2–5 μL obtainable during cochlear implant surgery, necessitates ultra-sensitive EV isolation techniques, such as immunomagnetic “nano pom-poms” targeting myosin VIIa-positive hair cell-derived exosomes. These constraints complicate both diagnostic validation and clinical scalability. Collectively, these anatomical and physiological discrepancies underscore the need for more translationally relevant platforms, including human inner ear organoids, non-human primate models, and advanced microfluidic systems, to bridge the gap between preclinical findings and clinical application (Frisina et al., 2018; Schmitt et al., 2021; Zhuang et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2023; Yu et al., 2019; Holdsclaw et al., 2025).

4.1. EVs in promoting regeneration of cochlear cells for sensorineural hearing loss

Over the past decade, EVs, including exosomes and microvesicles, have emerged as potential tools for regenerative therapy. They can modulate intercellular communication, reduce inflammation, and deliver therapeutic cargoes such as proteins, RNAs, and even gene-editing complexes to target cells (Warnecke et al., 2022; Perde-Schrepler et al., 2024). Small EVs (sEVs) have been shown to support hair cell survival, promote hair cell regeneration from inner ear stem cells, and facilitate postnatal nerve development in the inner ear (Jiang et al., 2022). Studies investigating the effects of EV on hearing loss are summarized in Table 1. These properties address EVs that deliver anti-oxidant compounds, regulatory microRNAs, and neurotrophic factors (e.g., BDNF) to cochlear target cells. By modulating cytokine profiles, they reduce harmful inflammation and activate survival pathways in both neurons and hair cells. Due to their nanoscale size, EVs can efficiently cross the blood-labyrinth barrier, reaching inner ear cells with high precision. These properties are key mechanisms underlying sensorineural hearing loss, positioning MSC-derived EVs as emerging therapeutic agents for preserving and potentially regenerating cochlear cells (Warnecke et al., 2020; Warnecke et al., 2022; Perde-Schrepler et al., 2025; Min et al., 2023; Warnecke et al., 2021). The miRNAs and proteins in cochlear-derived EVs (CDsEVs) are critical for normal hearing. For example, the fibroblast growth factor receptor 1 (FGFR1) within these vesicles may support cochlear hair cell survival. Integrating single CDsEV sequencing with single-cell RNA sequencing has helped identify the cochlear cells that produce these vesicles, revealing that Kölliker’s organ cells and supporting cells secrete the highest amounts (Jiang et al., 2024).

Most cell types secrete EVs, which carry a wide range of proteins, lipids, and nucleic acids, allowing them to strongly influence the behavior of target cells.

EVs can even be isolated for diagnostic purposes, offering a potential liquid biopsy approach for SNHL. Traditional methods, such as clinical audiometry or inner ear tissue biopsies, are either insufficient or carry a significant risk. To address this, researchers have investigated the use of perilymph fluid, accessible during surgery, as a source of diagnostic EVs.

To isolate inner ear-specific exosomes from the extremely small perilymph samples (2–5 μL), a novel ultra-sensitive immunomagnetic “nano pom-pom” technique was developed. This approach allowed, for the first time, the direct collection of sample material from living human inner ear hair cells by targeting exosomes expressing the sensory hair cell marker myosin VIIa (Zhuang et al., 2021). These findings not only confirm the presence of EVs in perilymph but also suggest that hair cells are a potential source (Warnecke et al., 2022). MSC-EVs have gained significant attention for their ability to promote tissue repair, modulate the immune response, and reduce inflammation. (Perde-Schrepler et al., 2024). Following cochlear injury, these EVs decrease pro-inflammatory cytokines and increase anti-inflammatory mediators, creating a more supportive environment for cell survival and regeneration (Warnecke et al., 2022; Warnecke et al., 2021). Additionally, MSC-EVs can deliver factors that protect hair cells and neurons, inhibit apoptosis, and activate regenerative signaling pathways. Recent preclinical studies demonstrate that EVs can be used to deliver CRISPR/Cas9 complexes to cochlear hair cells for gene editing. Engineered EVs have successfully transported CRISPR-Cas9 components to cochlear cells, effectively targeting genetic mutations that cause hearing loss. Briefly, the delivery of CRISPR/Cas9 through EVs resulted in a high on-target editing efficiency, with approximately 82% indels observed in Myo7a^{sh1} mutant fibroblasts *in vitro* and around 6% via EV-RNP *in vivo*. This was accompanied by a significant reduction in mRNA levels and a ~ 20 dB improvement in ABR threshold in Shaker-1 mouse cochleae over a period of 6 months. NGS did not detect any ototoxicity, oxidative stress, or off-target editing in hair cells, indicating low toxicity. Immunogenicity risks also appear minimal, as RNP expression is transient and EVs are biocompatible. Nevertheless, potential anti-Cas9 responses should be monitored in future immunogenicity studies (Pan et al., 2023). A significant advance in gene therapy for hearing loss was made by Bence György et al., who showed that exosome-associated adeno-associated virus (exo-AAV) vectors can efficiently deliver therapeutic genes to all inner ear hair cells, including outer hair cells, which are typically difficult to transduce. In both *in vitro* cochlear explants and *in vivo* cochlear injections, exo-AAV1 outperformed conventional AAV1, without affecting hearing or balance. This method partially restored hearing in a mouse model of hereditary deafness (Lhfp15 knockout), as evidenced by improved auditory brainstem response thresholds. These findings highlight exo-AAV as a biocompatible and efficient gene delivery system, offering a potential strategy for treating genetic sensorineural hearing loss by targeting cochlear hair cells more effectively than conventional methods. In addition, safety considerations for clinical translation include potential AAV immunogenicity and off-target effects. Histological analysis of transduced cochleae revealed no acute immune responses or inflammation, and electron microscopy demonstrated exo-AAV internalization without affecting hair cell ultrastructure. However, pre-existing neutralizing antibodies, which are common in humans, may reduce efficacy, and long-term T-cell responses have not yet been assessed beyond the study period. Off-target transduction was minimal, occurring mostly in hair cells, with low-level expression in supporting cells and none in spiral ganglion neurons. Dosage scaling also presents a challenge, as human cochleae are approximately 30 times larger than those of mice. Vector genomes, therefore need careful adjustment from the $\sim 10^9$ vg used in mice to avoid under- or overdosing, which could lead to inflammation or reduced effectiveness (Gyorgy et al., 2017). EVs have also been used to deliver drugs, including anti-inflammatory agents and pro-resolving mediators, directly to cochlear cells, bypassing barriers that limit other treatments. Studies show that small EVs (≤ 150 nm) carry pro-resolving proteins such as Annexin A1 and Galectins 1 and 3, have higher levels of eicosanoids, and more readily incorporate polyunsaturated fatty acids. In contrast, large EVs (>150 nm) are more efficient at carrying aspirin, lipoxin A4, and resolvin D1. Both EV types contain enzymes that produce eicosanoids, some of which can be pro-inflammatory (Kalinec et al., 2019). The study investigated the potential of MSC-sEVs to protect SGNs, a key contributor to SNHL, from

Table 1

Studies investigating the effects of EV on hearing loss. Abbreviations: MSC: Mesenchymal stem cell; SNHL: Sensorineural hearing loss; BM-MSC: Bone marrow-derived MSC; ABR: Auditory brainstem response; HEI-OC1: House Ear Institute-Organ of Corti 1; NIHL; Noise induced hearing loss; BDNF: Brain Derived Neurotrophic Factor; SGN: Spiral Ganglion Neuron.

Focus of study	EV source	Hearing Loss Type	Model/System	Outcomes [Ref]
Protective effects of MSC- EVs on cisplatin-induced damage to inner ear sensorineural cells	MSC	Ototoxic SNHL (cisplatin-induced)	HEI-OC1	Raising cell viability Decreasing ROS production and altering apoptosis Significantly lower the cytotoxicity Protects the inner ear from damage caused by cisplatin (Perde-Schrepler et al., 2025)
The possible therapeutic effects of EV-MSCs with Apelin ARHL	MSC	ARHL	An elderly mouse model with MSCs transplants and EVs that carry Apelin	MSCs turn into hair cell lineages in the inner ear Apelin in EVs makes M2 macrophages polarize Reduces inflammation, protects hair cells, and restores hearing in old mice It has both regenerative and anti-inflammatory effects for ARHL (Xu et al., 2025)
How MSC-derived exosomes protect auditory hair cells by controlling autophagy	UC-MSC	Ototoxic SNHL (neomycin-induced)	mouse SNHL model and cochlear explants and HEI-OC1 cell line	Reduction of hearing loss and hair cell death caused by neomycin Promoting endocytosis, which activated autophagy in hair cells Increasing cell survive Reduced oxidative stress and apoptosis in mitochondria (Liu et al., 2024)
Protection against SGN degeneration by intratympanic injection of MSC- sEVs	Rat BM-MSC	Degeneration of SGN associated with SNHL loss by Ouabain	Primary cultured rat SGNs (<i>in vitro</i>) and ouabain-induced SGN degeneration rat model (<i>in vivo</i>) treated	Prevents degeneration of spiral ganglion neurons Suggesting therapeutic potential for SNHL (Chen et al., 2024)
Assessment of the microRNA and proteomic characteristics of small EVs derived from cochlear tissue	Small EV produced from mouse cochlear tissue	Developmental changes relevant to sensorineural hearing function	Mouse cochlear tissue at different postnatal stages	The microRNA and protein cargo of cochlear sEVs changed with age Indicating roles in cochlear maturation and possible targets for inner ear development The molecular compositions of EVs are different in newborn mice and adult mice (Jiang et al., 2022).
How BDNF-sEVs protect against cochlear damage caused by noise	Human MSC	NIHL	Mouse model (CBA/J mice) exposed to noise; systemic intravenous delivery of BDNF-sEVs	significantly reduction in the loss of cochlear hair cells It also protected synapses and reduced oxidative stress and apoptosis up cochlear repair (Min et al., 2023).
Exosomes derived from CSGPC have protective effects against cochlear IRI.	CSGPC	Acute SNHL caused by ischemia-reperfusion injury	Mouse model of cochlear IRI	Inhibition of inflammatory factors (IL-6, IL-1 β , TNF- α , Cox-2) Promoted anti-inflammatory microRNAs (miR-21-5p, miR-26a-5p, miR-181a-5p) Lowered hair cell apoptosis and improved auditory thresholds after injury (Yang et al., 2021)
Protective and reparative effects of UCMSC- exosomes on cisplatin-induced outer hair cell loss and cochlear damage	Human UC-MSC	Ototoxic SNHL (cisplatin-induced)	Mouse	Increase in mmu-miR-125a-5p, mmu-miR-125b-5p, and mmu-miR127-5p expression in inner ear tissues May suppress inflammation or protect outer hair cells from damage. Exosomes contain higher levels of fibronectin, galectin-3, and certain growth factors Promotion of tissue remodeling and repair (Tsai et al., 2021)
MSC-exosomes protect cells from cisplatin-induced apoptosis through the HSP70 mechanism	Human MSC	Ototoxic SNHL (cisplatin-induced)	Mouse ex vivo cochlear explant mode	Reduction of cisplatin-induced ototoxicity in auditory hair cells Lower apoptosis in auditory explants by sending HSP70 Protect against ototoxicity Could be used as a treatment for SNHL (Schwob, 2002)
Intracochlear application of MSC-EV (Clinical)	Human UC-MSC	Person with bilateral hearing loss (Meniere illness)	Human	Feasible, safe and reduces surgical inflammations Better understanding of speech (Warnecke et al., 2021)
MSC treatment for NIHL and RNAseq analysis of protective/repair pathways	hWJ-MSC		Mouse	Important pathways: GABA receptor, CREB signaling, calcium signaling, and synaptogenesis. Reduction of inflammation markers like TNF α Raised levels of anti-apoptotic genes like bcl-2 Protection of cochlea after noise trauma at 4, 8, and 32 kHz (Warnecke et al., 2021)

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued)

Focus of study	EV source	Hearing Loss Type	Model/System	Outcomes [Ref]
How inner ear sensory hair cells are shielded from ototoxic damaging by exosomes including HSP70	Explanted mouse utricle	Ototoxic drug-induced (aminoglycoside, cisplatin) hearing loss	Primary mouse utricle cultures	Produces exosomes that contain (HSP70) in response to hot stress Interaction of the exosomal HSP20 with TLR4 receptor on hair cells Provides mechanism for hair cell survival in hot stress (Breglio et al., 2020)
Molecularly studying the miR-182-5p/ FOXO3 axis and how mouse inner ear stem cell exosomes protect against gentamicin-induced ototoxicity <i>in vitro</i> .	Mouse inner ear stem cells	Ototoxic SNHL (gentamicin-induced)	HEI-OC1	Attenuated gentamicin-induced apoptosis Less oxidative stress Better cell survival Higher levels of miR-182-5p and lower levels of FOXO3 (Lai et al., 2020)
Human MSC-EV protect against noise trauma	human multipotent stromal cells	NIHL	<i>In vitro</i> and <i>in vivo</i> models	BDNF is found in MSC-EVs An anti-inflammatory effect of EV Reduced IL-1 β gene expression Reduction of ABR threshold Improved survival, increased primary neurite growth, Partial hearing restoration, and rescue of the Corti organ (Warnecke et al., 2020)
	HEI-OC1 auditory cell line	Drug- and noise-induced SNHL	<i>In vitro</i> (HEI-OC1-EVs)	It is easy to load anti-inflammatory drugs and pro-resolving mediators into EVs These EVs could be used as nanocarriers to deliver these drugs to the inner ear to treat hearing loss caused by inflammation (Kalinec et al., 2019).

Fig. 4. A) Representative immunostaining images of inner hair cell synapses labeled with CtBP2 (anti-C-terminal binding protein 2) in cochlear surface preparations, displayed 14 days post-noise or sham exposure across various experimental groups. BDNF-sEVs significantly mitigated the noise-induced degradation of ribbon synapses at the basal turn of the cochlea, helping to preserve synaptic integrity. B) Immunostaining of neurofilament polypeptide in hair cells demonstrates that BDNF-sEVs offer significant protection to cochlear nerve fibers following noise exposure. C) Apoptotic cells were identified by performing the TdT-mediated dUTP Nick-End Labeling (TUNEL) assay in combination with co-staining using an anti-Myosin VIIa antibody. BDNF-sEVs treatment effectively lowered the number of hair cells undergoing apoptosis, as indicated by reduced TUNEL-positive staining following H₂O₂-induced damage. Reused with permission from (Min et al., 2023). Copyright © 2023 Elsevier B.V.

degeneration. In primary cultured SGNs, MSC-sEVs were found to promote neurite outgrowth and enhance growth cone development. These EVs carry components and activate signaling pathways associated with neuronal development and axon regeneration. In a rat model of SGN degeneration induced by ouabain, intratympanic injection of MSC-sEVs significantly improved SGN survival and reduced hearing loss. The treatment also suppressed apoptosis in SGNs, as indicated by reduced caspase-3 activation, decreased nuclear fragmentation and condensation, and fewer TUNEL-positive cells (Chen et al., 2024).

4.2. Role of EVs in protection against noise-induced hearing loss

Noise-induced hearing loss (NIHL) results from prolonged exposure to loud noise. While it can affect people of all ages, it is particularly common among younger individuals due to recreational noise exposure, such as continuous music listening with headphones. Over 50% of people aged 12–35 are at risk of developing NIHL (Chadha et al., 2021). EVs, especially MSC-EVs, show promise for protecting against and treating NIHL. EVs carry neuroprotective molecules and can modulate the immune response in the inner ear, minimizing noise-induced damage. Therapeutic factors, such as brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), can be loaded into small MSC-EVs (MSC-sEVs) to enhance their protective effects. In mouse models of NIHL, Xin Min et al. demonstrated that intravenous injection of MSC-sEVs loaded with BDNF increased cochlear BDNF levels (Fig. 4). Following noise trauma, treated cochlear hair cells exhibited restored myosin expression and phalloidin staining of the actin cytoskeleton, confirming the molecular and cellular protective effects. MSC-sEV treatment significantly reduced hair cell loss, preserved inner hair cell synapses by assessing anti-C-terminal binding protein 2 (CtBP2), and prevented degeneration of cochlear nerve terminals. Additionally, these EVs lowered oxidative stress and apoptosis in cochlear cells, demonstrating a strong neuroprotective effect against noise-induced injury (Min et al., 2023).

Demonstrating their immunomodulatory and neuroprotective potential, local administration of human MSC-EVs to the inner ear *in vivo* significantly reduced hearing loss and protected auditory hair cells from noise-induced damage. MSC-EVs also exert substantial effects on T cells and microglial cells, highlighting their role in modulating the inner ear immune environment. *In vitro* studies further show that MSC-EVs protect SGNs, underscoring their neuroprotective properties. This beneficial effect is partly attributed to the presence of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) within the vesicles, a key molecule that supports neuronal survival and function. Indeed, injecting MSC-EVs into the inner ear effectively reduced hearing loss and protected auditory hair cells, as evidenced by a reduction in ABR thresholds at 4, 8, 16, and 32 kHz (Warnecke et al., 2020). Following noise-induced trauma, MSC-EVs enhanced cell survival by upregulating anti-apoptotic signals such as Bcl-2 and suppressing pro-inflammatory cytokines like TNF- α in cochlear tissues (Warnecke et al., 2021).

4.3. Role of EVs in protection against drug-induced hearing loss

Drug-induced hearing loss occurs when certain medications negatively affect the inner ear. Aminoglycoside and macrolide antibiotics, such as gentamicin and azithromycin, are particularly ototoxic and are commonly prescribed for conditions like Meniere's disease, especially in developing countries (Rybak et al., 2021; Rauch et al., 2011). These drugs can damage cochlear hair cells, which are essential for hearing and balance, leading to hearing loss. Exosomes are released in response to cellular stress, such as heat or drug exposure. By interacting with the TLR4 receptor, exosomes help hair cells survive antibiotic-induced damage. Blocking exosome activity eliminates this protective effect, suggesting that exosomes could be harnessed therapeutically to enhance cell resilience (Breglio et al., 2020). In cell culture models, MSC-derived EVs improve the viability of cochlear cells exposed to the ototoxic drug cisplatin and reduce reactive oxygen species (ROS) production (Perde-

Schrepler et al., 2025). Their anti-inflammatory and regenerative properties also contribute to tissue repair and mitigate age-related cochlear damage (Warnecke et al., 2022). Furthermore, Huan Liu et al. demonstrated that exosomes derived from umbilical cord MSCs can protect auditory hair cells from damage caused by the antibiotic neomycin, highlighting their potential as a therapeutic tool for drug-induced hearing loss. The study showed that when hair cells internalize exosomes, they upregulate endocytic genes and promote endosome formation, which in turn triggers autophagy, a vital cellular process for maintaining cell health. This boost in autophagic activity reduced mitochondrial oxidative stress and prevented hair cell death, thereby preserving hearing function and mitigating neomycin-induced ototoxicity in both *in vivo* and *in vitro* models. These findings suggest that activating autophagy via MSC-derived exosomes, through an endocytosis-dependent mechanism, holds strong potential as a therapeutic strategy for SNHL caused by ototoxic drugs (Liu et al., 2024). Building on this, Stella Chin-Shaw Tsai et al. reported that UCMSC-derived exosomes deliver a cargo enriched with key miRNAs, including mmu-miR-125a-5p, mmu-miR-125b-5p, and mmu-miR-127-3p. These miRNAs play critical roles in inhibiting apoptosis and modulating inflammatory responses in the cochlea. Treatment with UCMSC exosomes normalized the expression of genes involved in oxidative stress, microglial activation, angiogenesis, and cytokine signaling, while upregulating genes linked to tissue remodeling, neural connectivity, trophic support, and synaptic transmission. By influencing both gene expression and the activity of cochlear microglia and endothelial cells, UCMSC exosomes foster a regenerative microenvironment that prevents outer hair cell loss and supports functional hearing recovery following cisplatin-induced ototoxicity (Tsai et al., 2021). Another study explored the potential of exosomes derived from mouse inner ear stem cells (IESCs-ex) in protecting against gentamicin-induced ototoxicity. These exosomes were shown to safeguard cochlear hair cells by reducing oxidative stress and apoptosis. *In vitro* experiments with HEI-OC1 cells exposed to gentamicin revealed that IESCs-ex enhanced cell survival, decreased oxidative stress markers such as malondialdehyde, and increased antioxidant enzymes, including superoxide dismutase, catalase, and glutathione peroxidase. Mechanistically, IESCs-ex exerted their protective effects by upregulating microRNA miR-182-5p and downregulating FOXO3, a gene associated with apoptosis. Notably, exosomes enriched in miR-182-5p further increased levels of the anti-apoptotic protein Bcl-2 while reducing the pro-apoptotic protein Bax. These findings highlight the miR-182-5p/FOXO3 axis as a key pathway through which IESCs-ex protect cochlear cells from gentamicin-induced injury (Lai et al., 2020).

4.4. Role of EVs in protection against age-related hearing loss

Age-Related Hearing Loss (ARHL), or presbycusis, is a progressive, bilateral decline in hearing that primarily affects the elderly. It impacts more than 65% of individuals over the age of 60 (Cunningham and Tucci, 2017). Oxidative stress and apoptosis of sensory and cochlear hair cells are key drivers of ARHL. Recent studies highlight the therapeutic potential of MSC-EVs in this condition. MSC-EVs protect sensory cells from oxidative stress and apoptosis, while also delivering bioactive peptides such as Apelin. This peptide promotes M2 macrophage polarization, reduces inflammation, and supports hair cell regeneration. In aged mouse models, these effects collectively contributed to restored hearing function (Xu et al., 2025).

4.5. Potential therapies involving EVs for inner ear damage

Exosomes and microvesicles, both types of EVs, have emerged as a potential therapeutic platform for treating inner ear damage. Preclinical and clinical studies are primarily focused on their regenerative, anti-inflammatory, and protective effects in sensorineural hearing loss caused by noise, aging, ototoxic drugs, and cochlear implantation. The

first reported clinical application of exosomes in humans was described by Athanasia Warnecke et al. in 2021. In this pioneering case, umbilical cord-derived MSC-EVs were administered during cochlear implantation in a patient with Ménière's disease, marking a breakthrough in the translation of EV-based therapies to clinical practice. This approach proved to be both feasible and safe, suggesting its potential as an adjuvant therapy to minimize surgical damage and accelerate tissue recovery. During surgery, electrocochleography recordings from the left inner ear confirmed that UC-MSC-EV infusion did not impair residual inner ear function. No signs of acute systemic or local toxicity, such as fever or allergic reactions, were observed within the first five days after surgery or during the subsequent 24 months of follow-up. Notably, speech intelligibility improved within the first year and remained stable into the second year after implantation. Ongoing clinical trials with larger patient cohorts are now underway to evaluate the broader efficacy of this strategy (Warnecke et al., 2021). However, significant challenges remain. Standardizing EV preparation to meet GMP requirements is still difficult, and researchers are actively exploring strategies to improve EV targeting to specific cell types and prolong their retention in the inner ear. To date, most findings remain preclinical, and large-scale human studies are required to establish optimal dosing, delivery methods, and the long-term safety and efficacy of EV-based therapies (Warnecke et al., 2022; Perde-Schrepler et al., 2025; Perde-Schrepler et al., 2025). All the preclinical efforts resulted in the approval of the first phase 1/2 clinical trial for intracochlear application of EVs during cochlear implantation to protect residual hearing in 2024, and the study protocol has been published under <https://euclinicaltrials.eu/> (EUCT number: 2024-512498-29-00, protocol code: ESCRT).

4.5.1. Delivery routes and outcomes

Intratympanic (IT) injection has a strong safety record, as it limits systemic drug exposure and carries a low risk of serious side effects. Most adverse effects are temporary, including ear pain, tympanic membrane perforation (which usually heals spontaneously), or vertigo, supported by extensive clinical experience with steroid delivery for sudden hearing loss. Intracochlear administration achieves optimal inner ear concentrations but carries higher risks, such as potential perilymph fistula, insertional trauma to hair cells or neurons, and transient threshold elevations during cochlear implantation procedures. Nevertheless, preliminary human EV trials have reported no acute toxicity or long-term functional impairment over 24 months. Intravenous EV delivery is generally well-tolerated, with infrequent immunogenicity or infusion reactions observed in MSC-EV studies. However, systemic biodistribution raises theoretical concerns regarding off-target effects in reticuloendothelial organs. These concerns are mitigated in preclinical NIHL models, where low doses have not caused ototoxicity or systemic inflammation. Intranasal administration appears highly tolerable, causing mostly mild nasal irritation and no CNS toxicity in exploratory studies. However, there is currently no safety data specific to the inner ear due to limited evidence of cochlear penetration. Until further research is conducted, intranasal delivery remains the safest noninvasive option (Swan et al., 2008; Pan et al., 2024; Warnecke et al., 2021; Szeto et al., 2020; Sung et al., 2019; McCall et al., 2010; Sánchez et al., 2025; Vlajkovic and Thorne, 2021).

4.5.2. Guidance for future preclinical studies

To improve comparability across studies, future preclinical research should report EV dosage using both a biologically relevant unit (e.g., total EV protein in μg or mg and/or particle count via nanoparticle tracking analysis) and the corresponding per-kilogram dose, alongside a detailed description of isolation, characterization, and administration protocols. For local delivery (intratympanic or intracochlear), fixed absolute doses (e.g., 10^8 – 10^{10} particles or 10–100 μg EV protein per ear in rodent models) should be normalized to body weight whenever possible. For systemic studies, the dose per kg, dosing frequency, and cumulative exposure should be clearly stated to facilitate translation to

clinical regimens. Functional endpoints should include serial ABR recordings across multiple frequencies and time points to assess both short-term protection and long-term preservation of hearing function. Where relevant, distortion-product otoacoustic emissions (DPOAEs) should be measured to evaluate outer hair cell health. Blinded histological analyses should quantify hair cell survival along the cochlear spiral, synaptic integrity at inner hair cells (e.g., by counting CtBP2/ribeye puncta), and spiral ganglion neuron density to link structural preservation with functional recovery. Additionally, quantitative assessments of inflammation and cellular stress, such as the expression of pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines, markers of oxidative stress, apoptosis (including caspase-3 activation, TUNEL positivity, and the Bax/Bcl-2 ratio), and, where relevant, autophagy and mitochondrial quality-control pathways, should be included. Additionally, quantitative assessments of inflammation and cellular stress, such as the expression of pro- and anti-inflammatory cytokines, markers of oxidative stress, apoptosis (including caspase-3 activation, TUNEL positivity, and the Bax/Bcl-2 ratio), and, when applicable, autophagy and mitochondrial quality-control pathways, should be included. These measurements will help connect EV cargo and mechanisms of action to therapeutic efficacy and allow standardized comparisons across EV sources, engineering strategies, and delivery methods (Pan et al., 2024; Warnecke et al., 2021; Warnecke et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2025).

The fundamental principles for safety evaluation of EV-based medicines are derived from the technical standards for the Research and Evaluation of Cell and Gene Therapy Products and adhere to Good Laboratory Practice (GLP). Studies conducted outside GLP settings should still be discussed and critically assessed for reliability, accuracy, and relevance to the overall safety profile of the therapy. It is important to establish both standardized toxicity testing and tailored safety evaluation systems based on the source of the EVs. Key aspects of EV safety investigations include neurotoxicity, genotoxicity, immunotoxicity, immunogenicity, and tumorigenicity. Primary considerations are the intrinsic safety of the EVs and the potential for contamination with mycoplasma, viruses, endotoxins, or residual media components. EVs are rapidly cleared from the body, predominantly via the liver and kidneys, and physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models can predict their absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion in preclinical studies. For inner ear applications, localized delivery, through routes such as the round window membrane or posterior semicircular canal, enhances targeted biodistribution to cochlear tissues while minimizing systemic exposure, as demonstrated in models of noise-induced hearing loss (Holdscraw et al., 2025; Takakura et al., 2024; Kumar et al., 2023; Kim et al., 2024; Kullar and Santa, 2025). Future preclinical studies should include functional endpoints such as ABR thresholds, DPOAEs, and vestibular sensory-evoked potentials (VsEP) to assess auditory and balance function after EV administration. Additional assessments should encompass immune response profiling (e.g., cytokine levels, macrophage activation), histopathology for ototoxicity, and long-term monitoring of hearing thresholds to ensure safety (Warnecke et al., 2021; Xu et al., 2025; Liang et al., 2022; Park et al., 2021).

5. Role of EVs in chronic rhinosinusitis and inflammatory disorders

Spontaneous regeneration of the olfactory epithelium is usually incomplete, highlighting the need for minimally invasive regenerative therapies (Huang et al., 2024). While interest in exosome-based therapies is growing, no studies have yet directly explored their application in olfactory disorders, an area that warrants future investigation. One notable exception is a recent study by Huang et al., which showed that intranasally delivered exosomes from umbilical cord mesenchymal stem cells (UC-MSCs) improved both motor and nonmotor outcomes, including olfaction, in a Parkinson's disease animal model. The treatment enhanced neuronal function in the olfactory bulb, promoted

dopaminergic neuron recovery in the substantia nigra, and reduced microglial and astrocyte activity, consistent with neuro-immunomodulatory effects (Rui et al., 2016).

5.1. Exosomes derived from the olfactory system

Stem cell-derived EVs, especially those from olfactory ectomesenchymal stem cells (OE-MSCs), show significant potential for immunomodulation and tissue regeneration (Keshtkar et al., 2018; Burrello et al., 2016; Rui et al., 2021). In animal models of systemic or inflammatory injury, OE-MSC-derived exosomes have been shown to suppress CD4⁺ T cell proliferation, reduce levels of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as interleukin-17 (IL-17) and interferon-gamma (IFN- γ), and increase regulatory mediators like transforming growth factor-beta (TGF- β) and interleukin-10 (IL-10). These effects collectively improve tissue function and mitigate damage (Tian et al., 2020; Kim et al., 2025). Such findings suggest that tissue-specific EVs may offer optimized cargo for repairing the olfactory epithelium. Further pre-clinical studies indicate that EVs from MSCs or OE-MSCs can reduce inflammatory markers, modulate glial and macrophage activity, and enhance neurogenesis and functional recovery (Xin et al., 2012). Proposed mechanisms for EV-mediated olfactory regeneration include the delivery of regulatory miRNAs such as miR-146a to suppress inflammatory signaling; the transport of neurotrophic factors and growth proteins including brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) and nerve growth factor (NGF), to support neuronal repair and axonal guidance; local immune modulation through induction of regulatory T cells and suppression of Th1 and Th17 responses; and antioxidant and anti-apoptotic effects in sensory and glial cells (Kim et al., 2025; Xin et al., 2012; Quiroz-Baez et al., 2020). EVs also show promise in diagnostics, as proteomic and miRNA profiling of exosomes may help differentiate between viral and neurodegenerative causes of olfactory dysfunction, as well as support monitoring of recovery and prediction of outcomes (Martin-Jaular et al., 2021; Tu et al., 2021; Petalas et al., 2023). Although this research area is still in its early stages, growing preclinical evidence provides a strong foundation for future therapeutic development. Future work should focus on comparative analyses of exosomes from different cellular sources and the creation of robust preclinical models that accurately reflect the complexity of human olfactory disorders.

5.2. EVs in chronic rhinosinusitis

Chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS), with or without nasal polyps (CRSwNP or CRSsNP), is a persistent inflammatory disorder of the sinonasal mucosa. It is characterized by type 2 and non-type 2 immune responses, epithelial barrier dysfunction, and microbiome alterations (Huang et al., 2024; Nocera et al., 2017). EVs actively contribute to CRS pathogenesis by delivering proteins that disrupt epithelial integrity and promote inflammation. For instance, P-glycoprotein (P-gp) carried in exosomes is linked to steroid resistance and enhanced type 2 inflammation, thereby driving disease progression (Kowal et al., 2016). EVs isolated from CRS patients show altered epithelial and antimicrobial protein profiles, with reduced protective factors and increased serum-derived components, which heighten susceptibility to infection and sustain chronic inflammation (Cha et al., 2021; Mueller et al., 2019). Dysregulation of coagulation and fibrinolysis pathways may contribute to fibroedema and polyp formation, explaining the frequent need for surgical intervention. Additionally, changes in the sinonasal microbiome, such as *Staphylococcus aureus* dominance and the presence of bacterial EVs, further amplify inflammation. Dysregulation of coagulation and fibrinolysis pathways may contribute to fibroedema and polyp growth, explaining the frequent need for surgical intervention. Additionally, changes in the sinonasal microbiome, such as *Staphylococcus aureus* dominance and the presence of bacterial EVs, further intensify inflammation, underscoring the importance of integrated analyses of EVs and the microbiome in CRS

(Huang et al., 2024). EVs are increasingly recognized as valuable diagnostic biomarkers in CRS. Specific proteomic and miRNA signatures, such as cystatin-2 (CST-2), periostin, pregnancy-associated plasma protein A (PAPP-A), and disease-specific miRNAs, have been linked to disease severity, comorbid asthma, and recurrence risk. Combined biomarker panels, for example, CST-2, periostin, and PAPP-A, may even help predict the likelihood of revision surgery. By differentiating between CRSwNP and CRSsNP, and between type 2 and non-type 2 endotypes, EVs can guide the development of personalized therapeutic strategies. Prospective monitoring of EVs after surgery may allow for the early detection of recurrence and timely adjustment of therapy (A J, 2023; Cheon et al., 2024). EVs in CRS are both a challenge and an opportunity. On one hand, they sustain inflammation and convey steroid resistance, positioning them as key drivers of persistent disease. On the other hand, these same characteristics make EVs potential candidates for biomarker discovery and therapeutic targeting (Kumar et al., 2024). However, challenges remain: reproducibility across research centers and validation of predictive EV panels. Integrating EV-derived proteomic and miRNA profiles with clinical endotyping could improve patient stratification and enable more precise, personalized treatment strategies. However, challenges remain: reproducibility across research centers and the validation of predictive EV panels are critical hurdles that must be overcome before EVs can be implemented in routine CRS management.

5.3. Comparative insights: olfactory disorders vs. chronic rhinosinusitis

EV-based approaches in olfactory disorders and CRS share the advantage of non-invasive sampling, yet their clinical objectives differ significantly. In CRS, the focus is on endotype classification, recurrence prediction, and targeting molecular drivers such as coagulation and fibrinolysis imbalance and P-glycoprotein (P-gp). In contrast, olfactory disorders prioritize neural regeneration and functional recovery, particularly through EVs derived from MSCs or OE-MSCs carrying neurotrophic factors and regenerative miRNAs (Moretti et al., 2025; Yoo et al., 2022; Sanchez et al., 2025). At the molecular level, both convergence and divergence are observed. EVs in both conditions carry proteins and miRNAs reflective of their cellular origin. However, CRS-derived EVs are enriched in coagulation-related proteins, mucosal and serum-derived components, and P-gp, while olfactory EVs predominantly contain neurotrophins, growth factors, and anti-inflammatory or regenerative miRNAs. Functionally, CRS-derived EVs amplify inflammation, recruit immune cells, and disrupt immune homeostasis, whereas olfactory EVs promote tissue regeneration, reduce apoptosis, enhance neurotrophic support, and modulate local immune responses. From a therapeutic perspective, CRS interventions focus on neutralizing pathogenic EV cargo and restoring mucosal homeostasis, whereas olfactory treatments rely on intranasal EV delivery to transport neuroregenerative agents, making formulation optimization critical for efficacy (Mueller et al., 2019; Moretti et al., 2025; Lochhead and Thorne, 2012). This comparison underscores the multifaceted nature of EVs: they can act as pathological drivers in one condition and regenerative facilitators in another. While CRS research has progressed primarily in biomarker discovery, studies on olfactory dysfunction highlight the regenerative potential of EVs. These findings show the context-dependent biology of EVs: in CRS, they mediate chronic inflammation, whereas in olfactory impairment, they promote neurogenesis. Deciphering the molecular determinants that drive these contrasting roles could open entirely new avenues for targeted therapies.

5.4. Intranasal route as a pathway for exosomes delivery in ENT: mechanisms, properties, and practical strategies

Intranasal delivery has emerged as a highly potential non-invasive method for administering therapeutic EVs to neural and nasal mucosal tissues (Lochhead and Thorne, 2012). This route is particularly valuable

because it partially bypasses the blood–brain barrier (BBB) and provides a direct anatomical connection to the olfactory epithelium and neural pathways (Lochhead and Thorne, 2012; Long et al., 2017). Experimental studies have shown that MSCs-derived exosomes (MSC-Exo), when delivered intranasally, can reach the olfactory bulb and hippocampus, eliciting anti-inflammatory and regenerative effects (Herman et al., 2021). In sinonasal disease models, nasal mucosa-derived exosomes have demonstrated the ability to transfer proteins like P-gp between epithelial cells, highlighting their capacity for safe and efficient mucosal penetration (Kowal et al., 2016).

5.4.1. Delivery routes and mechanisms

Intranasal EV administration can occur through three primary pathways: the olfactory neuronal route, the trigeminal nerve route, and paracellular or *trans*-epithelial transport (Gotoh et al., 2024). In the olfactory neuronal route, exosomes are taken up by sensory neurons in the olfactory epithelium and transported axonally to the olfactory bulb and higher brain centers. The trigeminal nerve route provides an alternative pathway to the brainstem, while paracellular transport, through intercellular spaces or via *trans*-epithelial mechanisms, particularly during inflammation or epithelial injury, can further enhance EV penetration (Ozturk et al., 2024).

5.4.2. Physicochemical properties and formulation strategies

Effective intranasal delivery of exosomes requires careful consideration of their physical and chemical properties. Particle size is crucial: exosomes between 30 and 150 nm are optimal, as they can penetrate the mucus layer and epithelial barriers efficiently. Larger particles tend to get trapped in mucus, while very small ones may enter systemic circulation too quickly, missing their target (Ozturk et al., 2024). Surface modifications are also critical. Hydrophilic or PEGylated coatings improve mucus penetration, whereas positively charged surfaces enhance mucoadhesion. Zeta potential influences both stability and penetration, with neutral or slightly negative charges offering the best balance (Dong et al., 2020; Moradi et al., 2022). To protect exosomal cargo such as miRNAs and proteins, stabilizing formulations like hydrogels or other protective additives are often used. Mucoadhesive hydrogels, which transition into a gel upon administration, extend retention on the mucosal surface, increasing uptake and allowing controlled release of therapeutic cargo. Conversely, mucus-penetrating coatings can accelerate transport through the mucus layer when rapid delivery is desired (Moradi et al., 2022; Rehman et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2015). Other innovative strategies include ligand-targeted exosomes, such as those decorated with RVG peptides, which enhance neuronal uptake and targeting. These approaches have shown efficacy in preclinical neurotherapy studies and could potentially be applied in ENT and neurological disorders (Premchandani et al., 2025; Alvarez-Erviti et al., 2011; Murali and Holmes, 2021). Intranasal EV delivery is especially considered for clinical translation because of the nasal cavity's anatomical proximity to the CNS and its non-invasive, patient-friendly characteristics. However, the formulation and design of EVs are critical. Achieving the right balance between mucoadhesion for prolonged retention and mucus penetration for deep tissue access is essential (Gotoh et al., 2024; Hashemi et al., 2024). Advanced carriers, such as thermosensitive hydrogels and ligand-decorated exosomes, represent exciting innovations. Nonetheless, their clinical success will ultimately depend on rigorous safety testing and reproducibility across large patient populations (Fan et al., 2022; Shen et al., 2025).

6. EVs for cartilage repair and regeneration

Cartilage defects in the craniofacial region, particularly in the ear, nasal septum, and larynx, pose major clinical challenges due to the avascular nature of cartilage and its limited capacity for self-repair. Traditional treatments such as autologous grafts and synthetic prostheses often produce suboptimal outcomes, including donor site

complications and poor tissue integration. Recently, exosomes have attracted growing interest as a cell-free therapeutic approach. By modulating the cartilage microenvironment and promoting regeneration through paracrine signaling, they offer a potential alternative to conventional methods (Chen et al., 2022; Kobatake et al., 2025; Oh et al., 2024; Wu et al., 2022).

In hyaline cartilage regeneration, exosomes derived from MSCs and chondrocytes stimulate chondrocyte proliferation, migration, and extracellular matrix (ECM) synthesis. They exert their effects through key signaling pathways, including PI3K/AKT, ERK, and WNT/ β -catenin. Furthermore, exosomes reduce inflammation by modulating NF- κ B signaling and delivering anti-catabolic microRNAs, such as miR-140, which help preserve the cartilage matrix (Longfei et al., 2025; Tan et al., 2024; Song et al., 2021; Chen et al., 2024). These findings are based on preclinical studies in articular (hyaline) cartilage models using *in vitro* or animal systems, and require further validation in clinical trials.

For elastic cartilage (auricular) regeneration, exosomes derived from adipose-derived stem cells (ADSCs) cultured in porous GelMA hydrogels have been reported in preclinical animal models to modulate microtia chondrocytes by transferring hsa-miR-23a-3p, which activates the PI3K/AKT/mTOR signaling pathway. These miR-23a-3p-enriched exosomes significantly increased cell proliferation, reduced apoptosis, and promoted cartilage matrix synthesis both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Notably, exosomes from higher-passage ADSCs (Exo 4 and Exo 6) demonstrated greater chondrogenic potential compared to those from early passages (Oh et al., 2024).

In a preclinical study, a three-dimensional (3D) culture system based on human ADSC spheroids was used to generate exosomes enriched with therapeutic microRNAs for auricular cartilage regeneration. By genetically modifying the exosomes with a chondrocyte-homing peptide (CHP), targeted delivery to ear chondrocytes was achieved even in inflammatory environments with M1 macrophage infiltration. In these models, CHP-modified exosomes enhanced chondrocyte proliferation, reduced apoptosis, and stimulated extracellular matrix synthesis, suggesting a potentially scalable approach for tissue-engineered auricular structures (Guo and Fan, 2023).

In a comprehensive study, Guo et al. examined the effects of EVs derived from auricular chondrocytes on the chondrogenic differentiation of ADSCs in preclinical models. They found that these EVs enhanced ADSC proliferation and migration, and promoted chondrogenic differentiation, as evidenced by increased expression of COL2A1, ACAN, and SOX9. Importantly, the EVs also stimulated elastin biosynthesis while suppressing the fibrotic marker fibrotic marker COL1A1, outperforming the commonly used chondrogenic inducer TGF- β 3 in these measures. These findings highlight the therapeutic potential of auricular chondrocyte-derived EVs for elastic cartilage regeneration and suggest they can enhance the regenerative capacity of ADSCs in otorhinolaryngology (Xavier et al., 2023). Preclinical studies also increasingly highlighting the importance of delivery strategies for translating exosome-based therapies into clinical applications in ENT. Biomaterial carriers, such as injectable hydrogels, composite scaffolds, and scaffold–exosome constructs, improve localization, sustained release, and support tissue regeneration. For instance, in preclinical rat models, alginate hydrogel–PCL/gelatin nanofiber scaffolds loaded with MSC-derived exosomes provided sustained release and promoted tympanic membrane regeneration. This approach underscores the translational potential of scaffold-based exosome delivery for ENT tissues, including the tympanic membrane and vocal folds, with enhanced structural integration (Chahsetareh et al., 2024). Key preclinical outcome measures include histology, tensile strength, and functional evaluations such as auditory brainstem response, allowing assessment of both structural repair and organ-level function (Ha et al., 2016).

7. EV-mediated drug delivery systems in otorhinolaryngology

The potential of EVs as drug delivery vehicles has been widely explored. Their effectiveness as nanocarriers is largely due to their phospholipid membrane, which enables fusion with lipid-rich barriers and allows EVs to cross biological membranes (Zhang et al., 2024). Additionally, EVs exhibit low immunogenicity and a prolonged half-life, making them highly suitable for drug delivery applications (Louis Jeune et al., 2013). Comparisons with established vectors, such as adeno-associated viruses (AAVs) and lipid nanoparticles (LNPs), are important for clinical decision-making. AAVs offer high transduction efficiency but are limited by small payload capacity and the prevalence of pre-existing neutralizing antibodies (Grieger Joshua and Samulski, 2005; Hagedorn et al., 2024). LNPs provide scalable manufacturing and efficient cargo loading but can trigger innate immune responses and lack the intrinsic homing capabilities of EVs (Bader et al., 2024; Yang et al., 2019). Synthetic nanoparticles allow tunable physicochemical properties but often suffer from poor biocompatibility and rapid clearance (Koh et al., 2023). In contrast, EVs combine high biocompatibility and low immunogenicity with the natural ability to cross biological barriers, making them a potential platform for drug delivery.

Despite these advantages, EV-based drug delivery remains relatively new in otorhinolaryngology, with research so far focusing primarily on inner ear disorders and head and neck cancers, highlighting both the promise of EV therapies and the need for further investigation. Methods for loading drugs into EVs generally fall into two categories: pre-loading, in which the drug is incorporated before EV isolation, and post-loading, where the cargo is introduced after EVs have been isolated. (Fig. 5) Pre-loading approaches include incubation, viral infection, and ultrasound combined with microbubbles (USMB). These methods preserve EV membrane integrity but provide limited control over cargo, exhibit low efficiency, and carry potential risks such as gene alteration and transfection toxicity (Joshi et al., 2021). Post-loading approaches can be either passive or active. Passive loading, typically via simple incubation, also maintains membrane integrity but suffers from low efficiency. Active loading techniques, such as electroporation, sonication, extrusion, or chemical induction, dramatically improve loading efficiency but increase the risk of EV aggregation and membrane damage (Joshi et al.,

2021). Furthermore, research indicates that different EV loading techniques can affect cargo integrity (Dzaman and Czerwaty, 2023).

One of the key advantages of using novel nanocarriers like EVs in otorhinolaryngology is their potential for inner ear drug delivery. The inner ear is protected by the blood-labyrinth barrier (BLB), which limits the effectiveness of systemically administered drugs. While intratympanic injection offers an alternative delivery route, drug leakage through the eustachian tube often occurs, requiring multiple injections and increasing the risk of tympanic membrane perforation or cochlear infection (Zhang et al., 2024). These limitations underscore the need for advanced delivery systems, such as EVs, to achieve higher drug concentrations within the inner ear. For example, György et al. investigated exosome-mediated gene delivery using EVs associated with Adeno-Associated Virus Serotype 1 (AAV1). They demonstrated that these EV-AAV1 complexes achieved significantly improved gene delivery to both inner and outer hair cells compared to conventional AAV1 vectors (Gyorgy et al., 2017). In a recent study, Holdsclaw et al. utilized EVs derived from the Round Window Membrane (RWM) for drug delivery (Fig. 6). By applying electroporation and sonication, they successfully loaded dexamethasone into the EVs and delivered them via intratympanic injection. Their findings demonstrated that these EVs significantly enhanced dexamethasone transport across the RWM, highlighting their potential as effective nanocarriers (Zhang et al., 2020).

Numerous studies have investigated the use of EVs as nanocarriers for HNCs. In a systematic review of 18 articles, Dzaman and Czerwaty reported that most EV-based drug delivery studies focused on miRNAs as cargo, while others explored small molecules, proteins, or chemotherapeutic agents (Palviainen et al., 2019). For example, Zhang et al. developed bovine milk-derived exosomes as carriers for oral squamous cell carcinoma therapy. They conjugated doxorubicin to the exosomes via a pH-sensitive bond that breaks under acidic conditions and incorporated endoperoxides and chlorin e6 (Ce6). Using ultrasonic oscillation, they generated an exosome–doxorubicin–anthracene endoperoxide derivative (Exo@Dox–EPT1). Upon thermal cycloreversion, the endoperoxides release singlet oxygen, enhancing cancer cell death. This system demonstrated both biocompatibility and therapeutic efficacy in treating OSCC (Fuloria et al., 2021). In another study, EVs isolated from BDNF-overexpressing MSCs were systemically administered to rats.

Fig. 5. Post-loading and pre-loading methods for loading drugs into exosomes. Reused with permission from (Joshi et al., 2021). Copyright © 2023 MDPI.

Fig. 6. They extracted EVs from the Round Window Membrane. Through electroporation and sonication, they encapsulated dexamethasone into the EVs and administered them by intratympanic injection. Reused with permission from (Zhang et al., 2020). Copyright © 2025 Elsevier B.V.

Despite BDNF being too large to cross the blood-labyrinth barrier, this approach successfully increased cochlear BDNF expression and protected against noise-induced hearing loss (Min et al., 2023). Overall, these studies highlight the versatility of EVs as nanocarriers in otorhinolaryngology.

However, scaling from benchtop isolation to clinical-grade production requires strict compliance with Good Manufacturing Practice (GMP) standards. Unlike synthetic drugs, EVs are complex, biologics, posing unique standardization challenges:

- **Batch-to-Batch Variability:** EV metabolite profiles are highly sensitive to cell culture conditions (Lener et al., 2015).
- **Potency Assays**
- **Release Criteria**
- **Storage and Lyophilization:** while freezing at -80°C is standard, clinical distribution requires more stable, cost-effective, and easy-to-use solutions. Lyophilization (freeze-drying) with cryoprotectants such as trehalose is being investigated to enable room-temperature storage (Use of Autologous Plasma Rich in Platelets and Extracellular Vesicles in the Surgical Treatment of Chronic Otitis Media [Internet]).
- **Regulatory Classification:** currently, the United States and the European Union classify them as biological medicines. However, specific guidelines for EV-based therapeutics may be needed, depending on their cargo (Vesicle-enriched Secretome Fraction (VSF1.01) for the Reduction of Cochlear Implant Surgery Related Trauma (ESCRT), 2024).

Nevertheless, their application in otorhinolaryngology remains nascent, with much of the potential still unexplored. The innovative nature of these approaches underscores exciting opportunities for further research across various otorhinolaryngological applications.

8. Case studies and clinical trials of EV therapy in otology

Currently, four clinical trials are investigating the use of EVs in otorhinolaryngology. At the University Medical Centre Ljubljana, a study (NCT04761562) with 100 needed participants is evaluating whether autologous platelet- and EV-rich plasma can enhance and accelerate tympanic membrane healing in patients who have undergone tympanoplasty for chronic otitis media (Application of Salivary and

Plasma Exosomes in the Diagnosis of Oral Leukoplakia Malignant Transformation and Prognosis Monitoring of Oral Cancer [Internet], 2024). The current status of this clinical trial is unknown. Another phase I/IIa trial (NCT06545175) is assessing the safety of an EV-enriched secretome fraction for reducing trauma associated with cochlear implant surgery (An Observational, Single-Institution Pilot/Feasibility Study of Exosome Testing as a Screening Modality for Human Papillomavirus-Positive Oropharyngeal Squamous Cell Carcinoma [Internet]). It is currently in the recruitment phase, with 11 participants needed. Additionally, two recently completed trials have focused on HNCs, although their results are not yet published. One study (NCT06469892) measured exosomal miR-185 levels in saliva and plasma on 225 patients to determine their potential in diagnosing the malignant transformation of oral leukoplakia and predicting oral cancer prognosis (Application of Salivary and Plasma Exosomes in the Diagnosis of Oral Leukoplakia Malignant Transformation and Prognosis Monitoring of Oral Cancer [Internet], 2024). Another trial (NCT02147418) explored the feasibility of exosome testing on 15 patients for early detection of HPV-positive OSCC (An Observational, Single-Institution Pilot/Feasibility Study of Exosome Testing as a Screening Modality for Human Papillomavirus-Positive Oropharyngeal Squamous Cell Carcinoma [Internet]). Moreover, another trial (NCT04453046) was registered in 2020 in patients with HNC to evaluate Hemopurifier plus pembrolizumab therapy. This approach involves depleting exosomes from the blood of these patients using the Hemopurifier device in combination with the standard-of-care therapy, pembrolizumab (Depleting Exosomes to Improve Response to Immune Therapy in Head and Neck Squamous Cell Cancer). This therapy required 12 patients but was terminated in 2022 due to a lack of eligible subjects.

While EV research in otorhinolaryngology is still in its early stages, these clinical trials highlight their potential across various therapeutic and diagnostic applications in the field.

9. Conclusion

Extracellular vesicles (EVs) are emerging as a versatile platform in otorhinolaryngology, bridging molecular mechanisms with translational and clinical applications. Their capacity to transport bioactive proteins, lipids, and nucleic acids underlies growing interest in EV-based strategies for tissue regeneration, immune modulation, and precision diagnostics. In this specialty, EVs have shown particular potential for

targeted drug delivery to the inner ear, neuroregeneration in olfactory dysfunction, and biomarker development in chronic rhinosinusitis (CRS) and head and neck cancers (HNCs). Their biocompatibility, intrinsic targeting properties, and suitability for non-invasive administration, especially via intranasal routes, further support their translational relevance. Despite these advantages, clinical implementation remains contingent on addressing several critical challenges. To accelerate progress, three immediate priorities can be identified. First, standardized reporting frameworks and harmonized methodologies for EV isolation, characterization, normalization, and quantification are essential, alongside large, multicenter validation cohorts to ensure reproducibility and clinical robustness. Second, systematic *in vivo* biodistribution, pharmacokinetic, and safety studies are needed to define optimal dosing, tissue targeting, and long-term effects across different otorhinolaryngologic indications. Third, scalable GMP-compliant production pipelines, coupled with validated potency and quality-control assays, must be established to support regulatory approval and clinical translation. EV-based therapies and diagnostics have the potential to meaningfully advance the management of otologic, rhinologic, and oncologic diseases, contingent on the resolution of key technical, biological, and regulatory challenges. Achieving this goal will require the coordinated integration of multi-omics profiling, optimized delivery strategies, and ligand-directed EV engineering to enable precise, safe, and reproducible clinical applications in otorhinolaryngology.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Farid Fotouhi: Writing – original draft. **Zeinab Nokhbedehghan:** Writing – original draft. **Maryam Khajavi:** Writing – original draft. **Farzad Taghizadeh-Hesary:** Writing – original draft. **Rafieh Alizadeh:** Writing – original draft. **Alimohamad Asghari:** Writing – original draft. **Maryam Daneshmehr:** Writing – original draft. **Athanasia Warnecke:** Writing – review & editing. **Eva Rohde:** Writing – review & editing. **Mario Gimona:** Writing – review & editing. **Seyed Mohammad Davachi:** Writing – review & editing. **Mina Aleemardani:** Writing – review & editing. **Zohreh Bagher:** Writing – review & editing. **Writing – original draft.**

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpharm.2026.126634>.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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